

How barriers towards plant-based food consumption differ according to dietary lifestyle: Findings from a consumer survey in 10 EU countries

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ARTICLE INFO

Keywords:

Barriers
Consumers
Diet shift
Europe
Plant-based diet

ABSTRACT

A diet shift towards a more plant-based food consumption is advocated for sustainable, health and ethical reasons. Still, a diet change remains a societal challenge. The objective of this paper is to identify how barriers towards plant-based food consumption are experienced according to dietary lifestyle in 10 European countries. A pan-EU consumer survey was conducted as part of Smart Protein Project. In total 7590 answers were obtained (49.5% women). Omnivores were more likely to score higher in the barriers to diet shift than vegetarians, vegans or flexitarians. Large effect sizes (*Eta squared* >0.1) were observed for the following barriers a) the lay belief that humans are meant to eat lots of animal-based meat; b) the expectation that plant-based food products would not be tasty enough; c) and the experience of not enjoying such products. Medium effect sizes (*Eta sq.* > 0.06) were observed for variables addressing nutrition related barriers “would not be filling enough” and “I would not get energy or strength from these products”. Promotion of plant-based food consumption should be targeted according to diet lifestyle, with focus on their sensory characteristics and on addressing cultural (lay) beliefs e.g. through knowledge sharing.

1. Introduction

Despite substantial social marketing investment in promoting healthy eating, that is following national and international guidelines (Pérez-Cueto et al., 2012), mainstream consumers in the EU still under-consume foods of plant origin that are markers of a healthy diet, namely, fruits, nuts, vegetables, legumes, beans, pulses and whole grains. At the same time, it appears hard to alter the overconsumption of meat, dairy and ultra-processed foods (often high in fat, sugar and salt, while low in dietary fibre, and linked to undesirable health outcomes) (Appleton et al., 2019; Dinnella et al., 2016; Lin et al., 2015; Naska et al., 2006). Europeans eat twice or more red or processed meat than the recommended levels and exceed sugar intake by several orders of magnitude (Coyle et al., 2020; Hielkema and Lund, 2021; Huseinovic et al., 2019; Mehlig et al., 2021; Moran et al., 2019; Törmä et al., 2021).

In 2018, the International Panel on Climate Change (IPCC and et al Masson-Delmotte, 2018) called for systemic transitions based on an

alarming need for urgent mitigation investments, policy instruments, acceleration of technological innovation and behavioural changes to avoid reaching the irreversible climate tipping point. In 2021, IPCC report further emphasized that “It is unequivocal that human influence has warmed the atmosphere, ocean and land. Widespread and rapid changes in the atmosphere, ocean, cryosphere and biosphere have occurred.” (IPCC, 2020; IPCC, 2021). In 2022, the latest IPCC report indicates that a dietary shift is a necessary demand-side action with climate change mitigation potential (IPCC et al., 2022). The concurrence of climate change and obesity, undernutrition is considered as a syndemic exacerbating the burden of health crisis worldwide (Swinburn et al., 2019). In 2019, EAT-Lancet Commission issued guidance for diets within planetary boundaries (Willett et al., 2019). In 2020, the Science Advice for Policy by European Academies (SAPEA) called for concerted actions, involving multiple actors including consumers, on multiple levels of governance to transition of the European food system towards a more sustainable one (SAPEA, 2020).

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<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2022.100587>

Received 26 April 2022; Received in revised form 31 July 2022; Accepted 12 August 2022

Available online 23 August 2022

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Although the food sector emissions are traced to each previous step prior to consumption (production, processing, retail, etc.), the proportion of emissions from processing and transport (“how”) are less important than the initial raw materials (“what”) (Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Ritchie and Roser, 2020; Springmann et al., 2020). The main contributor to greenhouse gas emissions from the food sector is livestock intensive farming (Hjorth et al., 2020; Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Springmann et al., 2020). Largest share (83%) of food related greenhouse gas emissions in the EU result from meat, egg and dairy production and only 17% from vegetable products (Sandström et al., 2018). Therefore, a dietary shift, which is a key element in climate change mitigation, should be focused in the direction of increasing the production and consumption of foods of plant origin, while reducing dramatically those of animal origin, particularly in the developed world. (Carter, 2019; Ritchie et al., 2018; Ritchie and Roser, 2020). This necessary dietary shift would require as the most desirable outcome that mainstream consumers increasingly adopt plant-based dietary lifestyles (e.g. vegetarian, vegan). The process of diet shift would have a large spectrum of different levels of adoption, exemplified by, e.g. large variability in flexitarians’ frequency of meat consumption (Derbyshire, 2016; Hielkema and Lund, 2021).

Behaviour change, in particular dietary change towards a plant-based diet is difficult to achieve, either at individual or societal levels (Barad et al., 2019; Bhana et al., 2018; Reisch et al., 2021; Stok et al., 2018). Commonly known barriers towards plant-based diet are e.g.: lack of skills, cognitions about balanced eating, perceived hardships such as access and availability, finding recipes as well as the perceptions of the inadequacy and tastelessness of a diet without meat (Hielkema and Lund, 2021; Pohjolainen et al., 2015; Reipurth et al., 2019). Also socio-demographics matter. Women in general are more prone to adopt plant-based diets (Nakagawa and Hart, 2019; Satija et al., 2019). This gender effect seems to be associated with the lay belief that meat consumption is a masculine feature (Briers et al., 2020; Kongsbak et al., 2016; Munt et al., 2017; Rothgerber, 2013).

Despite these barriers, some consumer groups have been changing their attitudes and acceptance towards pro-vegetarian diets (Knaapila et al., 2022), and by doing so, more and more consumers declare they are adopting new dietary behaviours such as flexitarianism or pescatarianism that are associated with a dietary shift (Appleton et al., 2019; de Gavelle et al., 2019; Faber et al., 2020; Wozniak et al., 2020). In particular, vegetarians in general consume predominantly foods of plant origin and have more concern for animal welfare and rights than omnivores or pescatarians; flexitarians are more aware of the health and environmental effects of meat consumption than omnivores. Current dietary lifestyle is one of the main predictors of the level of transition to a diet rich in foods of plant origin (Banyte et al., 2022; de Gavelle et al., 2019). However, to the knowledge of the authors, only few studies have compared attitudes and perceived barriers to dietary shifts across different countries and dietary lifestyles (Noguerol et al., 2021; van Loo et al., 2017). This study is part of the consumer studies conducted by the EU-Funded Smart Protein project that develops future-proofed plant-based protein supply chains. Consumer studies provide strategic insights into the sector. Therefore, the objective of this study is to evaluate differences on consumers’ perceived barriers towards consuming plant-based foods by dietary lifestyles in 10 EU countries, and hence, further inform strategies for a sustained dietary shift.

2. Method & design

2.1. Data collection

Data were collected during April/May 2021 through a large-scale questionnaire-based online consumer survey in Austria, Denmark, France, Germany, Italy, The Netherlands, Poland, Romania, Spain and the United Kingdom. This survey is part of the EU H2020 project Smart Protein (<https://smartproteinproject.eu/>). Respondents were recruited

by INNOVA, a market research agency, according to predetermined quotas for women and men (50/50), age groups (20% in each: 18-24y; 25-34y; 35-44y, 45-54y and 55-70y), and being responsible for grocery shopping. The quotas allow for cross countries comparison within categories. Informed consent was obtained by the agency, and data was available only in anonymous manner for the present study. External market research agencies ensure representative sampling by collecting data from their established panels in the relevant countries as well as sufficient statistical power for cross-country comparisons. (Malhotra, 2019).

The instrument was developed in English and translated professionally to the languages spoken in the target countries. The questionnaire included sociodemographic characteristics, such as age (yr), sex (female, male, other), education (elementary, secondary, superior), locality of residence (urban, semi-urban, rural), household composition. Relevant to this paper, the questionnaire addressed barriers towards adopting plant-based diets using a pre-tested scale (Banyte et al., 2022). Barriers were expressed as level of agreement or disagreement (Likert scale, from 1 = totally disagree, to 5 = fully agree) with 26 statements such as “I don’t want to change my eating habits or routine”, “Plant-based food products would not be filling enough”, “I think humans are meant to eat lots of animal-based meat”, “I wouldn’t get enough energy or strength from plant-based food products”, “Plant-based food products would not be tasty enough”.

2.2. Data analysis

Descriptive statistics for nominal variables are presented as proportions; continuous variables are summarized by their means and standard deviation. Differences on barrier scores were evaluated between diet lifestyles, country, gender, education and locality of residence with ANOVA and the effect sizes were evaluated with *Eta* squared (Lakens, 2013). As rule, the effect sizes were considered small if *Eta* sq. = 0.01, medium if *Eta* sq. = 0.06 and large if *Eta* sq. = 0.1. Data management and analysis were performed with SPSS 25®, and a *p* value < 0.05 was considered significant.

3. Results

In total 7590 responses were obtained, balanced over 49.5% women and 49.5% men, with the remaining classifying themselves as “other”. Majority (56%) lived in urban areas, 24% in suburban areas and 20% in rural areas. Most respondents reported having a good health status (79.5%). According to their dietary lifestyle, 60% were omnivores, 30% flexitarians, 3% pescatarians, 5% vegetarians and 2% vegans. When it comes to openness to dietary changes, 37% of respondents indicated that they do not want to change their habits or routines.

Table S1 in Supplementary Materials show the scores of each barrier statement by dietary lifestyle. All barrier scores were statistically different by dietary lifestyle (ANOVA, *p* < 0.001), except for the statement “Plant-based meals or snacks are not available when I eat out”. Omnivores tend to score higher in all barrier statements. Large effect sizes (*Eta* sq. > 0.1) were observed for the following barriers: a) the lay belief that humans are meant to eat lots of animal-based meat (*Eta* sq. = 0.11); b) the expectation that plant-based food products would not be tasty enough (*Eta* sq. = 0.10); c) and the experience of not enjoying such products (*Eta* sq. = 0.11). Medium effect sizes were observed for variables addressing nutrition related barriers “would not be filling enough” (*Eta* sq. = 0.09) and “I would not get energy or strength from these products” (*Eta* sq. = 0.09).

Regarding gender, women tend to score lower in all barrier statements (Table S5 in Supplementary material) and for the majority of statements they were statistically different from men (with the exception of “plant based foods (PBF) are not available”, “I need more information about PBF”, “my family won’t eat PBF” and “there is not enough choice of PBF”). Despite significant differences, *Eta* sq. in all cases

indicated small to very small gender effects.

Scores of barrier statements were different between involved countries. AU and DE tend to score lower than the others, suggesting a readier market for the diet shift in German-speaking countries. Main barriers were the lack of desire to change diet ($Eta\ sq. = 0.05$) as well as the beliefs around the insufficiency of a plant-based diet for energy ($Eta\ sq. = 0.04$), taste ($Eta\ sq. = 0.03$) and satiety ($Eta\ sq. = 0.03$) in DK, PO and FR (See Table S2 in Supplementary Materials). Respondents in DK, PO and ES score higher in not knowing how to eat without animal products ($Eta\ sq. = 0.02$). Respondents with elementary education would score higher than those with superior education. People in urban areas tend to score higher in the barriers, except for the statement "My family/partner won't eat PBF products". However, the country, education and locality effects were in all cases small to very small (Tables S2–S5 in Supplementary material). It is noteworthy that the means were usually low, indicating that on average EU and UK respondents did not perceive the statements as actual barriers.

4. Discussion

4.1. Strengths and limitations

To the knowledge of the authors, this study is a pioneer among pan-EU consumer surveys that addresses stated barriers towards shifting diets and increasing consumption of plant-based foods in 9 EU Member States and the UK (Cheah et al., 2020; Hielkema and Lund, 2021; Munt et al., 2017; Pohjolainen et al., 2015; Reipurth et al., 2019; van Loo et al., 2017). The strengths of this work are fivefold; first, the large sample as a whole and in each target country (Norman et al., 2012); second, the common methodology that allows for cross-country comparisons (Naska et al., 2006; Trichopoulou et al., 2001); third, the balanced gender and age distribution (Pérez-Cueto et al., 2010); fourth, the representation of dietary lifestyles that are prevalent in society (vegan, vegetarian) (National Research Council, 1988), and fifth, a pretested questionnaire (Banyte et al., 2022). This study has limitations to address; first, the quota sampling for equal age groups was intentional to reflect the stationary population pyramids in EU, displaying somewhat equal percentages across age cohorts. Although extrapolation to population level should be done carefully, our results are valid and representative within age groups and comparable between countries. Therefore, cohort bias is unlikely in the sample. Second, as with any cross-sectional study, this is a snapshot of consumers at the time of the survey, allowing to show associations, but does not allow for inferring causality. Third, as data collection was subcontracted to a market research agency, selection bias is possible. However, external market research agencies ensure representative sampling by collecting data from established panels in the relevant countries (Malhotra, 2019). Fourth, social desirability bias may exist in the responses; however, the reasons would be only speculative and not from our data. Our findings suggest that in this sample of EU citizens, the main experienced hindrances to diet shift are lay beliefs around plant-based consumption, taste expectations and the hedonic experience of plant-based foods, and the belief about the nutritional inadequacy of a plant-based diet.

4.2. Lay beliefs plant-based diets

The experience of barriers (Pohjolainen et al., 2015) related to a dietary shift is very likely rooted in a set of food related concepts held as truth by consumers. Moreover, such a belief system can be driven by food and nutrition myths, often poorly justified or contradicting scientific evidence (Chakona and Shackleton, 2019; de Gavelle et al., 2019; Florença et al., 2021; Kay et al., 2021; McKeown and Dunn, 2021; Sámano et al., 2020). Noteworthy, on average EU consumers in the 10 selected countries do not report higher degrees of agreement with their experience of the listed barriers, suggesting a departure from common beliefs regarding dietary shift within Europe. Therefore, it was

worthwhile to focus on group differences of interest.

This study found that the belief that humans are meant to eat meat is in line with what has been reported previously (Bianchi et al., 2018; Cheah et al., 2020; Hielkema and Lund, 2021; Knaapila et al., 2022). Compared to men, women are more prone to adopt predominantly plant-based food consumption. Such differences in behaviours have been associated to the belief that meat is a masculine feature (Banyte et al., 2022; Nakagawa and Hart, 2019).

The surge of the flexitarian consumer is noteworthy. In the first decade of this century, the proportion of Europeans who did not eat meat was relatively low and steady of about 5% (Pérez-Cueto et al., 2010; Verbeke et al., 2011), but now flexitarians (Derbyshire, 2016) -defined in this study as "I sometimes eat meat, but I am trying to reduce my meat consumption and often choose plant-based foods instead" together with other more plant-exclusive eating practices represent no less than 40% of our respondents. Such change in diet lifestyle should not be underestimated or considered as a fad. The steadiness and extent of the change rather reveals a societal trend in the demand for foods with a recommended profile (Noguerol et al., 2021), and foods of more natural and plant origin (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020; Asioli et al., 2017). Moreover, this societal trend encompasses norm violation of cultural habits (Hielkema and Lund, 2021; Reipurth et al., 2019), new ethical and political considerations (Beck and Ladwig, 2021; Bernstein and Dutkiewicz, 2021; Dickstein et al., 2020; Macallan, 2022), and the deconstruction of lay beliefs about what women and men should, or are allowed to, eat (de Gavelle et al., 2019; Eker et al., 2019; Krige et al., 2018; Varraso et al., 2019; Wozniak et al., 2020). As such, vegan men (in a plant-exclusive diet) challenge the stereotypical image of men in risky behaviours, and rather exemplify more conscious and healthier expressions of masculinity (Aavik and Velgan, 2021; Banyte et al., 2022).

In this study we found significant differences between women and men in their experience of barriers towards dietary change; however, the effect sizes were smaller compared to those of the dietary lifestyle. Yet, those experiences of barriers convert into subtle but significant differences between women and men, are linked to portion sizes, preferences, attitudes and food-related behaviours, which underscore disparities in their risk of disease and early death (Afshin et al., 2019; de Gavelle et al., 2019; Murray et al., 2020; Varraso et al., 2019). Hence, addressing gender differences in future interventions should particularly target the facilitation of healthier and more sustainable choices and behaviours among male consumers.

4.3. Lay beliefs on nutritional adequacy of plant-based foods

In this study, we found country differences in the beliefs towards the adequacy of plant-based diets. Most particularly in DK, FR and PO, efforts are needed to empower consumers to enable better-informed choices regarding a dietary shift. Many myths surround the transition to plant-exclusive diets (Borude, 2019). However, there is growing consensus that future sustainable healthy diets should be predominantly plant-based (Afshin et al., 2019; Willett et al., 2019). Consumption of limited amounts of animal sourced foods is often allowed by national nutrition guidelines, as they are considered nutritionally dense foods (Gabe and Jaime, 2019; Nordic Co-operation, 2021; Serra-Majem et al., 2007; Springmann et al., 2020; van Dooren et al., 2014).

Dietary recommendations have emphasized on promoting a shift towards plant-based eating with higher intake of fruits, vegetables and pulses due to their positive health effects in the prevention or delaying chronic disease and early mortality (Acosta Navarro et al., 2010; Baden et al., 2019; Borgia et al., 2015; Chang et al., 2019; Satija et al., 2019; Satija and Hu, 2018; Zheng et al., 2019). While a transition to a more plant-based diet will deliver both on sustainability and health (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020), it will be of pivotal importance to also communicate this effectively.

4.4. Considerations supporting a shift to sustainable healthy diets

With 37% of the survey respondents indicating that they don't want to change their diets, it becomes apparent that a communication strategy should be sought with focus on their potential individual contribution to sustainability. It is widely acknowledged that the food sector is a key actor in mitigating climate change (IPCC et al., 2022), and in particular reduction of methane emissions will result mainly of a change in consumption and demand for animal sourced foods (Clark et al., 2019; Poore and Nemecek, 2018; Prag and Henriksen, 2020; Ritchie and Roser, 2020). As only 17% food related greenhouse gas emissions in the EU result from vegetable products (Sandström et al., 2018), it seems sensible to keep encouraging the consumption of fruits, vegetables, pulses, other grains and their derivatives.

Diet change should take into account sociodemographic aspects. Although the effect sizes were very small, education level and locality of residence affects the experience of barriers to dietary shift as it has been reported for e.g. dietary patterns (Naska et al., 2006). Diet change behaviour is most sensitive to social norms and self-efficacy (Eker et al., 2019), and therefore, measures to change social norms, such as advocating for new defaults in foodservice (Attwood et al., 2020; Perez-Cueto, 2021; Saulais et al., 2019) may contribute substantially to adopting healthier and more sustainable dietary patterns, while empowering consumers to improve their food decisions (Nørnberg et al., 2016).

4.5. Tastiness and liking of plant-based foods

In this study, the taste expectation of plant-based foods and the hedonic experience have been found as important barriers towards dietary shift. Omnivores scored significantly higher than the other groups in the statement that plantbased foods would not be tasty enough (Mean 3.37, SD 1; $\eta^2 = 0.102$). Taste is a promising instrument to facilitate food behaviour change, as people would usually re-purchase foods they like (Turnwald and Crum, 2019). For many consumers the belief that unhealthy is tasty, or healthy is not tasty, needs to be challenged, as it further predicts undesirable health outcomes such as obesity and the consequent health risks (Briers et al., 2020).

4.6. On facilitating the diet shift

In the present study, issues of price, availability when eating out and information were the barriers with higher scores across all dietary lifestyles (Fig. 1, Supplementary Materials). This suggests a window of opportunity for innovation in the food sector. Planning and developing pleasurable meals based exclusively on plants is a booming area within food design and foodservice (Damsbo-Svendsen et al., 2020; Mouritsen and Styrbaek, 2020). Foodservice operators can contribute to improved out-of-home meal quality by making the new defaults plant-centered rather than meat-centered.

Promotion of diets with low carbon footprint at population level should be implemented as a just dietary transition that will reduce of 46–74% in greenhouse gas emissions from the food sector (Chai et al., 2019; Galli et al., 2020; Han et al., 2020; Sandström et al., 2018) while contributing to improved health at population level (Foscolou et al., 2020; Lin et al., 2015), and creating opportunities for new business and innovation (Aschemann-Witzel et al., 2020).

5. Conclusion

Promoting a diet shift towards plant-rich diets requires addressing experienced barriers. This study showed that the different experiences of barriers is mainly explained by dietary lifestyle. On average, EU and UK respondents seem to score low in the barriers towards diet shift opening a window of opportunity for interventions. Communication and behaviour change strategies should be targeted according to people's

current dietary lifestyle. Future interventions should address the lay beliefs regarding the necessity of meat in a healthy diet, and the experience of plant-based foods, with special focus on their sensory characteristics and the pleasure obtained from their consumption.

Author statement

FJAPC wrote the first version of the manuscript. All authors had substantial contribution to the conception and design of the study. Questionnaire was developed by LR, IF, KBB. Overall supervision was provided by JJS, HDS & FJAPC. Data analysis was performed by FJAPC, LR, MAR, IF and all authors contributed to the interpretation of data for this paper. All authors revised the manuscript for important intellectual content and approved it for submission & publication. All authors agree to be accountable for all aspects of the work in ensuring that questions related to the accuracy or integrity of any part of the work are appropriately investigated and resolved.

Implications for gastronomy

This study showed that strong focus should be given to the pleasure and sensory characteristics of plant-based foods to facilitate a dietary shift. The gastronomy sector has an important role to play to prepare and provide meals that are sustainable, healthy and ethical. In particular, and based on the present study, the gastronomy sector can contribute to changing the image of plant-based foods by incorporating them in the normal offer, making them the "centre" of the dish, highlight their pleasurable sensory characteristics, and by being part of changing the image and lay beliefs of what foods and meals are culturally acceptable. Moreover, the scores of the experienced barriers open a window of opportunities for the sector to increase the availability of plant-based meals and snacks for customers, and this for an affordable price.

Declaration of competing interest

None.

Acknowledgement

This work is part of Smart Protein project that has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 research and innovation programme under grant agreement No 862957.

Appendix A. Supplementary data

Supplementary data to this article can be found online at <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.ijgfs.2022.100587>.

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